

Ride 2Rail

TRANSFERABILITY AND RECOMMENDATIONS HANDBOOK

Deliverable D 6.4

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PARTNER	COUNTRY
UNION INTERNATIONALE DES TRANSPORTS PUBLICS (UITP)	Belgium
FIT CONSULTING	Italy
OLTIS GROUP	Czech Republic
FSTECH	Italy
CEFRIEL	Italy
CERTH	Greece
EURNEX	Germany
EURECAT	Spain
POLIMI	Italy
UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE	United Kingdom
UNIFE	Belgium
UIC	France
UNIZA	Slovakia
ELLINIKO METRO (previously ATTIKO METRO)	Greece
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FV-Helsinki	Finland
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REPORT CONTRIBUTORS			
Name	Beneficiary Name	Short	Details of contribution
David Sarfatti	UIC		Lead author
Giuseppe Rizzi	UITP		Contributor/Involved in the Task/WP6 leader
Alessio Tardivo	EURNEX		Official Reviewer
Stefanos Gogos	UNIFE		Official Reviewer

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Content

Consortium of partners	3
Disclaimer	4
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
2. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	7
3. BACKGROUND.....	8
3.1. Shift2Rail context.....	8
3.2. Ride2Rail context.....	8
3.3. Work Package 6 context.....	9
4. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	13
4.1. Deliverable objectives.....	13
4.2. IT Scope.....	14
4.3. Ride2Rail Data Flow.....	15
4.4. Inputs.....	15
5. HELSINKI RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS.....	16
6. BRNO RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS.....	18
7. PADUA RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS.....	19
8. ATHENS RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS.....	21
9. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TRANSFERABILITY.....	23
9.1. Detailed recommendations from each demo site	23
9.2. Main recommendations for Ride2Rail project transferability.....	26
9.3. Additional comments about Legal framework.....	28
10. LINK AND ACCESS TO THE RIDE2RAIL RESULTS.....	30
11. CONCLUSIONS.....	31
12. REFERENCES.....	32

List of Figures

Figure 1: Pictures from the Paris Transferability Workshop

Figure 2: Data Flow in R2R

Figure 3: Automated Robobus tested in Helsinki

Figure 4: Brno demo area

Figure 5: Padua demo site

Figure 6: Cover of the Engagement event

Figure 7: Athens demo area

Figure 8: IP4 Description

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The project implemented demonstrations of the Ride2Rail service in four locations – Padua, Italy; Athens, Greece; Brno, Czech Republic; Helsinki, Finland. A critical aspect of these demonstrations is to disseminate and transfer their performance against the aims of the project, and in terms of supporting sustainability actions in these locations.

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the possible transferability approach to be used in WP6 and for Ride2Rail as a whole. This followed the Open Call for Transferability launched in 2021 and the Transferability Workshop held in Paris in 2022.

2. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
PT	Public Transport
QAIC	Quality Assurance and Innovation Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
TSP	Travel Service Provider
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

3. BACKGROUND

3.1. Shift2Rail context

Shift2Rail is the first European rail initiative to seek focused research and innovation and market-driven solutions by accelerating the integration of new and advanced technologies into innovative rail product solutions. Shift2Rail promotes the competitiveness of the European rail industry and meets changing EU transport needs. Research carried out under this Horizon 2020 initiative develops the necessary technology to complete the Single European Railway Area.

The delivery of Shift2Rail is based around five Innovation Programmes (IPs); the focus of this report is IP4 – IT solutions for attractive rail services. To become a more attractive option, rail must respond to customer needs to support anytime, anywhere, door-to-door, intermodal journeys encompassing distinct modes of transportation. Rail must achieve interoperability with other transport modes and mobility services, with regions, cities and people engaged in social and economic activities, and with the key elements of the supply chains which can make rail products and services available to those people. In order to achieve this, rail needs to take due advantage of the increasing connectivity of people and objects, the availability of European Global Navigation Satellite System-based locations, the advances in cloud computing, big, linked and open data and the propagation of internet and social media. The step towards sharing data needs to be considered and progressively developed, in order to enable service developers to provide connected travellers with the services they need and expect.

3.2. Ride2Rail context

A key aspect of delivering more attractive services is by delivering end-to-end (or first- and last-mile) travel services that enable rail as their core mode of mobility. This can be challenging in a rural environment, where connectivity to rail is problematic. It is also relevant in urban or peri-urban environments where there may be poorer provision of public transit or congestion of roads.

Contributing to Shift2Rail's IP4, Ride2Rail's overall objective is to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating the efficient combination of flexible (ridesharing) and scheduled transport services (rail, bus, and other public transport services), thus enhancing the performance of the overall mobility system. Ride2Rail should, in particular, address the first and last mile problem by offering a wider range of transit options, while harnessing the capacity of single occupancy vehicles, along with existing, or future, demand responsive transit.

Ride2Rail aims to integrate multiple (public/private/social) data sets and existing transport platforms for promoting an effective ride sharing practice of citizens, making it a complementary transport mode that extends public transport networks.

The objectives of the Ride2Rail project are:

- To develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services, integrating real-time information about public transport and ride sharing;
- To facilitate the comparison and the choice between multiple options/services classified by a set of criteria, for example environmental, travel time, comfort, cost;
- To encourage carpooling (and ride sharing acceptance) as complementary for public transport;
- To enhance the performance of the overall mobility system, reducing road congestion and environmental impact, reinforcing the mobility offer in rural and low-demand areas;
- To combine travel offer classifications and software components, integrating them into existing collective and on-demand transport services;
- To induct the access to high-capacity services thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing and payment features;
- To design, develop and test in four real demonstrators a set of software components for the IP4 ecosystem, including an enhanced Travel Companion and the crowd-based Transport Service Provider;
- To produce recommendations for replicability.

3.3. Work Package 6 context

The activities performed in WP6 were targeted at disseminating the ongoing project results and activities to the widest possible audiences. Some of the most important events in transport research and innovation have been organized between M31 and M36. Project partners and the coordinator had the chance to present and discuss the project in several meetings (on national/international level), to submit of abstracts and posters, to draft articles and to perform additional communication activities.

The Taks 6.3 started in M12. The Leader UIC worked on the MS19 “Launch of Open Call For Transferability”, in order to foster the replicability of the RIDE2RAIL solutions in other locations. This was the first step towards the D6.4 Transferability and recommendations handbook submitted that constitutes this document.

After the first, second and third iterations of the open call (officially launched in July 2021), no positive feedbacks have been collected and, according to the calendar, the call was re-opened (but with a broader audience). 100 additional municipalities and potentially interested stakeholders have been contacted and UIC, the leader of this task, did also involve POLIS, EUROCITIES and MaaS Alliance. No candidates were found, none

of the city replied. Promotion for the open call was performed on social media and online, and also with direct mailing.

It can be stated that numerous actors were extended invitations to participate. These invitations were sent to a large range of cities for the Transferability Call and to for the Transfrability Workshop which was conducted in an online format. Additionally, it is worth noting that the project partners have leveraged their extensive networks to disseminate the results. Notably, UITP (including its committees, working groups, other project partners, thematic newsletter subscribers, and the broader public transport community at large), UNIFE (members of its technical platforms), and UIC were among the entities engaged for this purpose.

In a first stage, as UIC saved some budget dedicated to the Stakeholders' Workshop, incentives (reimbursement of travel expenses) was planned to be given to the winners of the open call for transferability in order to visit the demo cities and participated to the local events in demo sites. This was included in the RIDE2RAIL amendment n.1.

In a second stage, as no European city wished to participate to the Open call for transferability, the Task leader decided to Organize on November 23rd, 2022, a Transferability Workshop and invite all to participate and learn more about the RIDE2RAIL results.

To allow the workshop to be more efficient, all speakers were requested to come to Paris and participate in person. A total of 40 participants met on the transferability workshop held on the afternoon of 23 November 23rd, 2022, at the UIC headquarter in Paris and online. They were equally distributed between in person and online (connected via Zoom).

The participants were coming from different organisations such as Railways Operators from Europe but also from China, Japan, India and Marocco. And Île-de-France Mobilités, department of "Intermodalités et Nouvelles Mobilités", a Ride2rail target audience as Regional Transport Authority attend the meeting. The Ile-de-France Region, the City of Paris and the seven other Ile-de-France departments are members of Île-de-France Mobilités. It carries the global vision of Ile-de-France transport which it entrusts. The participation of these actors to the workshop can be a potentially powerful tool to promote the project and its developments in another geographical context outside the 4 demo areas. Interactions have been established with the participants, and in particular Île-de-France Mobilités, department of "Intermodalités et Nouvelles Mobilités" showed interest in knowing more about the project. This can, in theory, contribute to reach new audiences and potentially additional actors interested in knowing more about the project experience and get some insights on how to replicate (partially or totally) the Ride2Raile experience. The workshop outcomes were particularly positive in this sense, with interactions and shown genuine interest, particularly on the tools developed to enrich the Travel Companion (offer categorizer, offer matcher and ranker, incentives provider, agreement ledger).

The workshop demonstrated the achievements of the EU Shift2Rail RIDE2RAIL project with its various efficient pieces of software available and their deployment in three large European cities for multimodal transportation (at the time of the event, Padua demo

was not yet performed and only an overview with some details about the planned work have been presented). On top of the above mentioned participants, it is important to note that other actors coming from IP4 took part to the event, either on site and online: some partners participating to the IP4 project IP4MaaS, some other actors participating on CFMs (Call for Members) side, representing the IP4 projects COHESIVE, CONNECTIVE, EXSTENSIVE. A specific agenda slot was dedicated to CFMs, in particular for a presentation/overview on the IP4 ecosystem and its functionalities, characteristics, tools, features and how they can support the project demos.

Figure 1: Pictures from the Paris Transferability Workshop

All the presentations and the recording of the event are available on the UIC dedicated meeting webpage: <https://uic.org/events/ride2rail-transferability-workshop>

4. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE

4.1. Deliverable objectives

The objective of Task 6.3 is to transfer results and technologies developed across different demo locations both, to other relevant mobility stakeholders in those specific demo sites and beyond (for further roll-out), as well as to all project partners not directly involved in these activities.

This deliverable 6.4 contain all relevant information about the demonstration activities carried out within RIDE2RAIL project and their results, and additional information about the project and its context. Relevant links and references to public documentation available online are listed in this document, including the digital repository for the pieces of software developed by the RIDE2RAIL consortium, that constitutes a very powerful project outcome made freely available to any potential actor. Lessons learnt have also been included in the document, together with recommendations for transferability of results, mainly coming from the Transferability Workshop organized in Paris and the demo experiences themselves. These are useful in case interested non-project related actors want to start exploring the project potential for replicating the RIDE2RAIL experience, fully or partially, in other geographical contexts. Limitations and barriers, emerged as lessons learnt from the project demo experience, are listed and need to be taken into account by anyone willing to replicate the project experience but also by any actor dealing with the tools utilized in RIDE2RAIL. .

This action contributes to transfer the usability of measures implemented, from the demo locations to other potentially interested stakeholders, on a regional level and to a small/rural City group with the aim of achieving further potential replication.

RIDE2RAIL designed, developed and tested in 4 real demonstrators (Padua, Brno, Athens, Helsinki) of a set of software components for the S2R IP4 ecosystem, including an enhanced Travel Companion and a so-called crowd-based Transport Service (CB TSP), a component acting as a real TSP, fostering valuable combination of flexible and scheduled transport services. The advanced Travel Companion is an enriched version of the Shift2Rail Travel Companion, integrated with components developed by RIDE2RAIL partners.

The approach used for managing the RIDE2RAIL project is based on several main pillars:

- Definition of choice criteria for journey planning;
- State of the art, analysis and recommendations for a successful ridesharing in a multimodal journey.
- Identification of requirements and specifications for complementary travel expert services in the Shift2Rail IP4 ecosystem;
- Definition of algorithms for optimal synchronisation of shared-mobility and mass transit;

- Development of RIDE2RAIL components (Offer Categorizer, Offer Matcher and Ranker, Incentive Provider, Agreement Ledger, Crowd Based TSP, Driver Companion);
- Implementation of the demos in four Europe-wide demo sites through identification of the current mobility situation in the demo sites, looking at potential improvements for those locations, creating of an evaluation framework and acquiring the KPIs;
- Evaluation and Impact Assessment, carried out per each demo site.

Employing the successful collaboration, the IP4 solution, represented by the Enhanced Travel Companion and the Driver Companion applications, have been demonstrated in four demo sites, Athens, Helsinki, Brno and Padua. Despite the challenges linked to the post-COVID new mobility patterns and other operational challenges of different nature, these tools have been tested in real environment, with a total of more than 120 testers overall. To provide quality feedback, a complex evaluation carried out, monitoring a set of pre-defined KPIs. These KPIs have been measured using qualitative and quantitative data from both the IP4 ecosystem and the users' feedback collected via questionnaires, in Brno also through daily reports.

4.2. IT Scope

Five softwares modules were developed in the Ride2rail projects:

- Offer Categorizer (T.3.1): a service to compute scores for each offer returned by the Travel Companion with respect to a set of Offer Categories.
- Offer Matcher and Ranker and Incentive Provider (T.3.2): a tool that learns contextual preferences of users and ranks classified trips accordingly.
- Crowd-based Travel Service Provider (T.3.3) and Driver Companion (T.3.4): collect and publish ridesharing offers.
- Agreement Ledger (T.3.5): a digital ledger based on blockchain technology that register events related to ridesharing and secures smart contracts related to it.

4.3. Ride2Rail Data Flow

Figure 2: Data Flow in R2R

4.4. Inputs

All Demonstrations sites have deployed and tested the Ride2Rail IT architecture. Their results will help the transfer of the measures implemented, with the aim of achieving further potential replication.

All results and the main facts about the execution of the 4 demos are included in D4.4: Demo execution report. The purpose of this deliverable is to report on execution of demonstrations held in the four areas chosen as test sites. It reports all main elements from the planning phase (which structure has been described in the “D4.1 Demo implementation plan”) to the end of activities for all demo sites and, finally, offers some considerations on achieved results and lessons learnt. The report also covers detailed aspects on the execution of every single demo (Athens, Helsinki, Brno and Padua).

Details on monitoring issues or data collecting are reported in the “D4.5 Demo monitoring report”.

5. HELSINKI RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

The Helsinki demo involved the operation of an automated electric bus, known as the Robobus, between September 25th and November 17th, 2021. This bus was available free of charge to all users and operated in two modes: scheduled and on-demand. In the on-demand mode, passengers could request the bus using a web-based application. The service received positive feedback from users, who found it easy to use, comfortable, and convenient. Despite encountering technical issues such as sudden braking, passengers were satisfied with the overall experience. Over the course of the demo, 1112 passengers utilized the Robobus, covering a distance of over 2000 kilometers. Valuable suggestions for improvement included increasing the size of the vehicle to accommodate more passengers and extending the service hours to cater to different travel needs.

Figure 3: Automated Robobus tested in Helsinki

The RIDE2RAIL functionalities have been tested, as much as possible integrated with existing Helsinki Region Transport (HSL) mobility platform (e.g. public transport routeplanner) through available open-source interfaces. The tests were performed for two weeks in Helsinki region on 3-16. October 2022.

Helsinki demo was organized for a limited test group only. Testing the apps need certain background information and explanation of how the apps work. The test group of 20 persons consisted finally of people recruited by the demo actors Forum Virium Helsinki and Metropolia University of Applied Sciences. 17 persons answered the survey. Between drivers and passengers, a total of around 30 people could use the applications at least once.

The tests started on time and applications worked for the two weeks. Reported problems were solved promptly.

The functionalities used were Navigation, Journey planner, Trip tracking and Group travelling. Functionalities planned but not used because of the HSL sandbox environment were Issuing, Validation and Inspection.

6. BRNO RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

The Brno demo site, located in the South Moravia Region of the Czech Republic, focused on testing the Ride2Rail ridesharing platform. The primary objective was to address the transportation needs of commuters traveling from the Znojmo district to the city of Brno.

Figure 4: Brno demo area

The demo took place for two weeks, from October 31st to November 13th, 2022. The test group consisted of 60 participants, including both passengers and drivers. The applications tested in this demo were the enhanced Travel Companion and Driver Companion, offering a wide range of functionalities previously identified by the demo team. The demo resulted in 1946 rides, with 76 of them being shared rides. Valuable feedback was collected through surveys and daily reports from passengers and drivers, providing insights into the user experience, functionality, and areas for improvement.

7. PADUA RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

The Padua demo site, situated in the Veneto Region of Italy, aimed to support rural commuters and enhance the efficiency of public transportation services. The demo focused on encouraging carpooling and ride-sharing as complementary modes of travel, with the objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and alleviating traffic congestion. The demo took place from April 17th to April 21st, 2023, primarily targeting commuters traveling to/from the University of Ca' Foscari in Padua. The Driver and Travel Companion apps were tested during this period, assessing various functionalities such as preference & profile settings, trip planning, trip sharing, navigation, issuing, booking, and traveler's feedback. The demo witnessed 79 app downloads, with more than 50 participants engaging in a total of 387 rides. Feedback from users highlighted the ease of use of the apps, although some users experienced challenges related to ticket purchasing and redundant questions. These insights provide valuable input for refining the user experience and addressing the identified issues.

Figure 5: Padua demo site

During the demo, both the Driver and the Travel Companion apps were tested, while the specific functionalities put under the spotlight included Preference & Profile, Trip Planner, Trip Sharing, Navigation, Issuing, Booking, Traveller's Feedback, Guest User, Offering a Ride, View your Journey and Collaborative Space. In order to ensure the largest possible number of testers, a student engagement plan was structured through emails sent by university staff to students' mailboxes, including "Save the date" emails, reminders and an Engagement event on the Padua Demo and the TC and DC apps that took place on April 14th, 2023. The goal was to train the Testers so that they could fruitfully tackle the demo. No incentives and/or gifts were provided to Testers so as to encourage participation in the demo. The demo included the testing of demonstration scenario with the support of project partners OLTIS, FIT CONSULTING and CEFRIEL.

Figure 6: Cover of the Engagement event

8. ATHENS RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

The Athens demo site aimed to improve the connectivity between low-density areas and public transportation, particularly by integrating demand-responsive ridesharing services with existing modes of transportation such as metros. The demo tests were conducted over a span of four days, specifically from July 18th to July 22nd, 2022. A total of 28 individuals participated in the testing process, with 19 acting as passengers and 9 as drivers. Out of these participants, 17 filled out the survey, which was incentivized with rewards for travellers and for drivers. Feedback received from the Athens demo site included suggestions for improving the registration process, optimizing the award code recognition system, and ensuring accurate translations in the application.

Figure 7: Athens demo area

After having described the results from all demos, it is important to specify that RIDE2RAIL demo structure tried to involve both the urban and the rural aspects. Helsinki was a purely “urban” demo, while in Padua, Brno and partially Athens, the apps were tested in urban and rural context (this is particularly true in Padua and Brno, where the vast majority of users were commuters). The South Moravian authority organizing the public transport in the whole region, Athens metro and Padua heavy rail were strongly committed to the project, with the aim to allow passengers to have a door2door experience combining ride sharing and public transport (mainly rail in Athens and Padua). It is important to note that Sustainability transportation is one of the most important and satisfying outcomes of the project, once again transversal to the different demo sites. Users agreed on the importance to reduce the single car occupancy and on the high potential brought by a widespread development and utilization of Ride2Rail concept of using ridesharing as a feeder for Public Transport. The outcomes of the project, summarized in the D5.3 about “Evaluation and Impact Assessment” confirmed the positive impacts on the different KPIs identified, some of them related to CO2 emissions, linking the project to the S2R MAAP and allowing the project to make some concrete steps towards the achievement of the Shift2Rail ambition to strengthen the role of rail as the backbone of the mobility, eliminating barriers to interoperability and providing solutions for full integration, covering traffic management, vehicles, infrastructure and services, aiming to achieve faster uptake and deployment of projects and innovations, increasing capacity and enhancing flexibility and reliability,

9. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TRANSFERABILITY

This paragraph recaps the recommendations developed through the experience in RIDE2RAIL demos, the transferability workshop results and all inputs gathered along the project.

9.1. Detailed recommendations from each demo site

During the tests, the use of the OpenMaaS API was successful, although some results differed when displayed in the Travel Companion.

In the table below, the major challenges identified in the demos are listed, with possible solutions identified to better address/correct them. These solutions are mainly targeted to CFMs or IP4 ecosystem managers, as the main issues emerged affecting the technology utilized at demo level.

Challenge	Possible Solution
Vocabulary and logic comprehension	Emphasize user experience by simplifying vocabulary and logic in the ridesharing apps to make them more intuitive.
Route suggestions	Ensure accurate and relevant route options by addressing issues related to specific routes and surprising via points.
Limited communication capabilities	Enhance communication features between passengers and drivers by adding location sharing capabilities and improving overall coordination.
Short testing period	Extend the testing period to increase user engagement and obtain more comprehensive feedback for continuous improvement.

It was recommended to place more emphasis on user experience during app development, as some users found the vocabulary and logic of the apps difficult to understand. Integrating the Driver Companion as a feature of the Travel Companion would make the use of ridesharing functionality easier.

Some bizarre routes and results were observed in the apps, with not logic connections, long waiting times, options with more than 1 hour walking. Furthermore, the apps did not allow users to make changes in the rides offered or communicate with the driver or passenger. User location sharing was restricted due to anonymization of participants' data for GDPR compliance, hindering smoother communication between the passenger and the driver. Occasionally, the Travel Companion showed routes with no names or suggested waiting times of up to 6 hours.

Some test users had difficulty understanding the survey questions or found them too detailed for the two-week testing period. It was recommended to extend the testing

period to increase user engagement and allow users to reuse the applications multiple times.

In summary, important outcomes from the tests include the need for comprehensive testing and clear explanations of app functionality to ensure a positive transformation in mobility habits. The development process prioritizes user experience and aims to address reported issues to refine and optimize the ridesharing experience. The exceptional features of the apps may sometimes resemble technical errors due to their sophisticated and innovative design. Enthusiastic test users provided valuable feedback, highlighting their eagerness to contribute to the app's improvement. Testing the apps in a later phase of development would yield more fruitful results, enabling comprehensive refinement and enhancement based on valuable insights.

For the successful replication of Ride2Rail activities, it is crucial to engage closely with the Call For Members (CFMs) project partners responsible for managing the ecosystem. These partners, including Thales, Indra, HaCon, and CS Group, provide access to tools, integration guidelines for transport service providers (TSPs), an overview of functionalities, and training on tool usage. Close collaboration and effective communication among all stakeholders, including CFMs, technical partners, and demo leaders, are essential for replicating Ride2Rail results. The project partner EURECAT, leading the development of Ride2Rail functionalities, should be engaged for further information and assistance.

Despite the above outcomes, it is important to note that the project, and in particular the activities carried out before, during and after the 4 demos, allowed the consortium to get very useful information and positive feedback gathered via the interactions occurred with users via surveys and direct involvement in the demo activities. Most of these impacts are included in the above mentioned D4.4 and, more in details, in D5.3, dedicated to "Evaluation and Impact Assessment". A pre and post demonstration evaluation were carried out. Pre-demo evaluation used the baseline values of pre-defined Key Performance Indicators to perform a baseline appraisal of each demo site while in post-demo calculated the actual values of KPIs after the demo execution were compared to performance targets and KPIs of each site. In addition, the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method was used to obtain weights to allocate specific values to the different stakeholder priorities. The stakeholders' priorities were clustered around the four key impacts expected for topic S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019.

The project reached a huge number of testers, and those who accepted to be involved, enthusiastically participated to the project activities, providing valuable feedback that can be very useful for improving the IP4 ecosystem and its tools, in order to increase their quality and the overall user experience. It is important to note that almost everywhere, regardless of the geographical context and the specific demo conditions, users highly rated the usability of the applications/tools used (above 58% for DC and TC, using the standardized System Usability Scale, exceeding the target of 50%, and

indicating that participants applauded the ride-sharing concept, even at low TRL¹. These percentages suggested good usability for the application in a demo context. The surveys collected among users involved also confirmed what found in the project early stages (conversational survey and literature review), i.e. that the criterion “quickness” is considered the most important criterion for commuters to choose their mode of transportation. “Reliability” follows in the ranking, “price” comes third indicating that passengers are willing to pay a bit more if the transport is fast and reliable. “Comfortability” owns the fourth place and is followed by the criterion of “environmentally friendly” transport. Having door-to-door and short transport are ranked in the middle of the choice criteria. The last positions are attributed to: health, multi-tasking, social and panoramic²³.

As stated in the conclusion of the “evaluation and impact assessment” exercise, it came out that there is great potential to adopt ride-sharing and increase PT ridership. Despite the shorter duration of the demo, in Athens and Brno targets of several KPIs were exceeded such as KPI#3 (completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app), KPI#4 (completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app) and KPI#5 (completed commuter trips with R2R app).

The estimated priorities when designing a ride-sharing service across demo cities represented the Research community, Public Authorities, Critical Infrastructure Providers, PT Operators and Software company. The aggregated results showed that the top priority is considered the increase of public transport ridership which is followed by the improvement of rail connectivity. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, a lot of effort is placed at EU level to recover and even increase PT ridership and this is reflected also by the estimated priorities per city and in overall.

Ride-sharing has demonstrated a great potential for feeding PT and increasing its ridership. It is important to note that this is one of the most important and satisfying outcomes of the project, once again transversal to the different demo sites. Users agreed on the importance to reduce the single car occupancy and on the high potential brought by a widespread development and utilization of RIDE2RAIL concept of using ridesharing as a feeder for Public Transport. The robobus in Helsinki was also a huge success, with people willing to see it as a regular service in the city, serving a growing area not well connected by the current network.

The above positive findings have also been confirmed by the exercise/survey carried out in the Newcastle area and once again presented in D5.3. From this survey, it appeared clear that the Ride2Rail concept compares favourably with current concepts

¹ More information on RIDE2RAIL D5.3, “Evaluation and Impact Assessment”.

² More information on RIDE2RAIL D2.4 “Final conceptualization of choice criteria and incentives”.

³ More information on RIDE2RAIL D2.5 “Recommendations and criteria for successful ride-sharing in the IP4 ecosystem”.

of ride-sharing in the area. Participants were more willing to use Ride2Rail (particularly for leisure purposes), and to use it more regularly, in comparison to current levels of organised lift sharing. Also, Ride2Rail compares favourably with other forms of potential sharing to connect with rail services. While conventional taxi is preferred for occasional trips, Ride2Rail compares as well or better for more regular uses, up to several times a week. Finally, the choice criteria comparison indicates some of the reasons why travellers would use Ride2Rail (that is particularly valued in terms of being cheap, environmentally friendly, supporting multitasking on a trip, being sociable and avoiding road congestion). In terms of comparison with public transit, Ride2Rail compares favourably in terms of being cheap, providing door-to-door travel, and being sociable. Once again, this confirms the WP2 already mentioned findings in terms of choice criteria. Ride2Rail is perceived as having the potential for delivering a cost effective alternative to public transit and car travel.

9.2. Main recommendations for Ride2Rail project transferability

Based on the experiences and feedback gathered from the demo sites, several recommendations for the transferability and future implementations of ridesharing solutions can be made.

While each demo site presented unique challenges and solutions, several common aspects emerged:

1. **User Experience:** All demo sites emphasized the importance of user experience, suggesting that user-friendliness is a universal requirement for ridesharing apps.
2. **Improving Communication:** Enhancements in communication features were recommended across the board, highlighting its significance in facilitating user-driver interactions.
3. **Testing Duration:** Extending the testing period was a shared recommendation to improve user engagement and gather more valuable insights.
4. **Ride2Rail Concept:** The concept of using ridesharing as a feeder for public transport received positive feedback and showcased its potential across different locations.

Emphasizing user experience: Ensuring that the vocabulary and logic used in the ridesharing apps are user-friendly and intuitive, making it easier for users to understand and navigate the platform.

Integrating Driver Companion functionality: Incorporating the Driver Companion features into the Travel Companion app to provide a seamless and integrated user experience, enabling passengers to easily find and connect with available drivers for ridesharing.

Addressing issues related to specific routes: Resolving any issues related to specific routes or unexpected suggestions, ensuring that the app provides accurate and

relevant options for users. In some cases, for some Origin Destination entered in the route planner in Helsinki, the results displayed were too long, including surprising via points. The accuracy of timetable data and stations locations should perfectly fit the route planner functionality. This needs permanent maintenance to be able to correct quickly the right data on this specific routes which provokes different bug types (wrong time, wrong locations,..)

Enhancing communication features: Improving the communication features between passengers and drivers, such as adding location sharing capabilities, to facilitate coordination and enhance the overall user experience.

Extending the testing period: Extending the duration of the testing period to increase user engagement and allow for multiple app usages, which can provide more comprehensive feedback and insights for further improvements.

Overall, there exists a prevailing sentiment that the tool was favorably received by users, with a consensus that there is a need for further technical improvement.

The technical improvements involves several key aspects:

Enhancing Tool Flexibility : to improve the flexibility of the tool to ensure it can adapt seamlessly to the procedures, standards, and processes required for operators, TSPs (Third-Party Service Providers), and other actors involved.

Reducing Rigidity: A reduction in the tool's rigidity is essential. This means reducing the necessity for organizing specific instructional sessions for actors on how the ecosystem functions.

User Authentication and GDPR Concerns: Improvements in addressing GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) issues are necessary to ensure compliance and data privacy. Allowing users to use their actual usernames instead of predefined credentials will enhance the user experience.

Despite the above, within the framework of a research project, which currently operates at a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) comparable to Ride2Rail project, the results can be considered satisfactory, also because users have been duly informed and in some cases also trained. The IT tools developed and used in the project follow a structure and language in line with IP4 (to do so, a lot of interaction was established with CFMs from the very beginning, to understand the ecosystem and develop something in line with it). In terms of interaction, the JU, IP4 and its actors have always been kept into consideration both for invitation at events/project activities and for dissemination of material.

To move forward and facilitate the Ride2Rail replicability, it is important to further improve the IP4 ecosystem by making it more flexible, less rigid, self-explanatory/user-friendly, and capable of seamlessly integrating all actors (all these efforts are to be done by CFM or whoever actor manages the ecosystem). It is essential to improve the tools and the ecosystem. This improvement aims to streamline the integration of operators and actors, making the entire process smoother and, as a result, more qualitative for users and TSPs.

9.3. Additional comments about Legal framework

Regarding the CIT (International Rail Transport Committee), it's worth noting that the legal issues within the project were not particularly serious. Most matters were already covered by the consortium, collaboration agreements, project obligations agreed upon by partners, and internally validated terms and conditions. Although CIT was invited to workshops and the final event, their participation was not successful. But they did provide their input on

- Combined Rail with Bus (coach), international carriage is a subject for a rail section to the “Convention concerning International Carriage by Rail (COTIF) of 1999 and its Appendix A the “Uniform Rules concerning the Contract of International Carriage of Passengers by Rail (CIV) and in so far as it is applicable in the various countries and to the services in question, to Regulation (EU) 2021/782 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2021 on rail passengers’ rights and obligations
For international journeys for which a part of the route or the entire route is travelled with a bus, the carriage by bus is subject to Regulation (EC) No 181/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 February 2011 concerning the rights of passengers in bus and coach transport. Special conditions of carriage may contain rules that benefit the traveller more, these may apply in addition.
- Combined Rail with private car which is not yet subject to any law (as know by CIT). CIT is not dealing with individual transport as car, bicycle, scooter or taxi-like services.

On addressing GDPR and “user authentication” issues, it needed to be addressed by the IP4 platform owner/manager/developer and from all actors involved in organizing the demonstration activities.

On addressing IP Rights and Replicability, within the project context, Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) were established with specific partners to enable the sharing of information and materials. This process was facilitated by other project partners as well. While this approach may present a potential barrier to replicability, it was deemed

acceptable within the project due to prior commitments, collaboration agreements, and other relevant factors. To extend this approach on a larger scale, legal support is necessary, and actors must be willing to share information and data, which is a contemporary challenge.

IP4 building blocks (BBs) and deliverables associated with IP4 technology demonstrators (TDs)

IP4	TD4.1 Interoperability framework	BB4.1_1 Reference Ontologies and resolvers BB4.1_2 Services registry BB4.1_3 Converter Tools BB4.1_4 Semantic discovery, query, aggregation Engines	→	D4.1_1 Package resolvers
	TD4.2 Train Travel Shopping	BB4.2_1 Travel shopping orchestrator BB4.2_2 Meta-Travel solution constructor BB4.2_3 Travel expert managers BB4.4_1 Collection of static data BB4.4_2 Collection of dynamic-data BB4.4_3 Real-time event processing BB4.6_1 Data management	→	D4.2_1 Integration of multi-modal shopping BBs
	TD4.3 Booking & ticketing	BB4.3_1 Orchestration of ticketing mechanisms for multi-modal journeys BB4.3_2 Operations of ticketing back-office including lifecycle of parameters BB4.3_3 Validation of entitlements (e.g. card-centric, EMV)	→	D4.3_1 Integration of multi-modal booking and ticketing BBs
	TD4.4 Trip ticketing	BB4.1_1 Collection of static-data BB4.4_2 Collection of dynamic-data BB4.4_3 Real-time event processing	→	D4.4_1 Integration of trip-tracking mechanisms BBs
	TD4.5 Travel companion	BB4.5_1 Secured-cloud based platform (e.g. preferences) BB4.5_2 Interaction through smart devices BB4.5_3 Geo-navigation functions BB4.5_4 Device tapping functions	→	D4.5_1 Integration of travel companion BBs
	TD4.6 Business Analytics Platform	BB4.6_1 Data management BB4.6_2 Descriptive and predictive analytics BB4.6_3 Visualisation	→	D4.6_1 Integration of Business Analytics features BBs
	TD4.7 Overall IP4 Coordination and demonstration		→	D4.7_1 IP4 Ecosystem Release D4.7_2 End-user centric ecosystem D4.7_3 Co-modal ecosystem demonstration D4.7_4 Large scale MaaS demonstration

Figure 8: IP4 Description

10. LINK AND ACCESS TO THE RIDE2RAIL RESULTS

To access a comprehensive collection of public documents related to the project, EURNEX maintained the Zenodo community, where they diligently keep track of all the project's public documents. By visiting the following link, a wealth of valuable resources can be explored:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/ride2rail/?page=1&size=20>

EURECAT, a prominent contributor within the Ride2Rail initiative, has made significant technological advancements that have greatly impacted the project. These advancements include the development of essential functionalities such as the offer categorizer/ranker, crowd-based Transport Service Provider (TSP), and agreement ledger. All these functionalities have been seamlessly integrated into the enhanced S2R Travel Companion. Furthermore, as part of their efforts, the project has successfully delivered a Driver Companion, enriching the overall experience for all stakeholders involved. The Travel Companion Personal Application, enriched with R2R functionalities and the Shift2Rail IP4 framework, forms the solid foundation of the robust RIDE2RAIL IT architecture.

To facilitate easy access and promote collaboration, EURECAT has made all these remarkable software components freely available on GitHub. By visiting the following link the full potential of these components is downloadable:

<https://github.com/Ride2Rail>.

In the realm of application deployment, Docker emerges as an invaluable tool that enables the seamless automation of deploying applications within lightweight containers. This technology empowers applications to function efficiently across diverse environments. Capabilities and advantages of Docker can be explored as the following link provides detailed documentation:

<https://docs.docker.com/language/java/deploy/>

Finally, after analysis of demo outcomes, the Consortium, together with project Coordinator UITP, has published a Project Brief recapping project results, which is accessible online:

https://cms.uitp.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/RIDE2RAIL_Final-Leaflet.pdf

It received substantial attention, evidenced by multiple downloads and considerable appreciation from the audience.

11. CONCLUSIONS

RIDE2RAIL takes great pride in their extensive work, encompassing design, development, and testing in four real-life demonstrators located in Padua, Brno, Athens, and Helsinki. These demonstrators showcase a remarkable array of software components for the S2R IP4 ecosystem. Notably, they include an advanced Travel Companion and a crowd-based Transport Service Provider, both contributing to a seamless and personalized multimodal mobility experience in diverse environments. This visionary approach greatly facilitates the widespread acceptance and adoption of these innovations in the market. It's important to note that the advanced Travel Companion is an enhanced version of the renowned Shift2Rail Travel Companion, meticulously integrated with components developed by RIDE2RAIL partners.

Furthermore, the achievements and breakthroughs realized in these diverse RIDE2RAIL demo locations are not confined to the specific stakeholders involved. The transfer of results and technologies extends its reach to other relevant mobility stakeholders within these demo sites, facilitating further expansion and implementation. Moreover, even entities not directly associated with these activities can benefit from the knowledge and resources made accessible through the various repositories in this document.

This endeavor holds significant potential, as it not only transfers the effectiveness and practicality of implemented measures from the demos to the regional level but also aims to replicate these positive outcomes in small and rural cities. By broadening the scope of impact, RIDE2RAIL seeks to create a lasting transformation and foster further replication opportunities.

The Ride2Rail European Shift2Rail Project has successfully demonstrated the potential of ridesharing platforms and applications in different demo sites across Europe. The Helsinki, Brno, Padua, and Athens demos have provided valuable insights and feedback for further improvements and refinements of the ridesharing solutions. The recommendations for transferability outlined in this report will guide future implementations of ridesharing platforms in different regions, taking into account user experience, functionality, and user engagement to ensure the successful integration of ridesharing services with existing transportation systems.

12. REFERENCES

D2.4 “Final conceptualization of choice criteria and incentives”

RIDE2RAIL D2.5 “Recommendations and criteria for successful ride-sharing in the IP4 ecosystem”

D5.3, “Evaluation and Impact Assessment”

